

EXPERT SYSTEMS AND COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN: A PRODUCTIVE MERGER

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the merger of expert system and computer aided design technology to achieve a highly effective engineering workstation. The objective of the paper is to present the application of expert system concepts to CAD environments to show how artificial intelligence can act as a design assistant. This concept is demonstrated by a recent, successful software development effort to implement a digital circuit CAD tool enhanced by an expert system for educational use. We discuss the implementation of a CAD tool used in the Department of Electrical Engineering at the Air Force Institute of Technology. The use of graphics, simulation and expert systems are combined to construct an effective CAD workstation running on PC computer systems. The paper presents the use of graphics technology to provide schematic capture which, when coupled with a data base system, provides the necessary environment for a rule-based expert system. The CAD tool demonstrates the use of design heuristics, meta-knowledge and integrated circuit data to construct a forward chained reasoning mechanism for detecting design errors. The concept is extendable to other graphics oriented CAD tools. We describe operational experience with the tool and present summary performance measures which serve as possible predictors of other candidate system performance. We summarize our experience and discuss issues which influence the merger of knowledge-based models and computer aided design.

INTRODUCTION

The engineering profession has overwhelmingly adopted the use of computer aided design tools in virtually every discipline and area of practice. Computer design tools range from simple calculators to elaborate computer modeling and simulation packages. The net effect of computer aided design is more effective use of talented design staff and a technology multiplier which brings modern design experience within the reach of everyone on a design staff. We argue that the marriage of expert systems with computer aided design tools is an extension of the technology multiplier which allows diagnostic analysis of design decisions based on rules of thumb, experience or explicit design guidance. We show how this marriage of technologies can be accomplished with an example taken from the field of digital systems design.

The design of digital circuits is cumbersome and prone to errors. Current estimates show that a circuit designed with 5 integrated circuits has less than a 50% chance of working, due to wiring errors, when power is first applied. As the complexity increases, the probability of the circuit working on the first try decreases rapidly.

Design errors fall into two categories: wiring or logic errors. Wiring errors consist of improperly connected gates, missing connections, violations of fanout, and feedback or race conditions. Logic errors, which are more complex to detect, require knowledge of intended circuit function.

This research designs, develops, and tests an expert system which captures circuit connectivity via a graphics interface and decomposes digital circuits into subproblems described by database technology in order to detect wiring errors. Information needed to connect chips together is viewed as knowledge base information for the expert system. Information such as number of pins, value of each pin (input, output), type of chip, etc., are represented in a database. The interconnections between integrated circuits are evaluated within

the expert system. This research merges an expert system tool with database techniques in a two-step approach that provides wiring assistance to a design engineer in a CAD environment.

Digital Design Goals

Digital circuits can be designed using combinational or sequential logic. A combinational circuit consists of logic gates whose outputs are determined directly from the present state of the inputs, without consideration of the previous inputs. On the other hand, sequential circuits employ 'memory elements' in addition to logic gates. Their output is determined by the present inputs and the state of the memory elements. Consequently, sequential circuits depend not only on present inputs, but also the past inputs [13]. The design process of a digital circuit is very cumbersome and prone to errors. The design must be decomposed into the input and output signals, boolean functions, and logic diagrams before it is ready for implementation. Mano [13] describes the "classical method" for implementing digital circuits as having the following design objectives:

- minimum number of gates,
- minimum number of inputs to a gate,
- minimum propagation time of a signal through the circuit, and
- minimum number of interconnections.

Quite often the application drives the implementation of the circuit making it difficult to satisfy all of these constraints all of the time. The classical method assumes that, given two circuits performing the same function, the one with the fewer gates is preferable because it will cost less. This is not always the case with integrated circuits.

Mano [13] cites that it may be more economical to use as many of the gates from an already used package, even if the number of gates is increased. Moreover, some of the gate interconnections are internal to the chip and it is more economical to use as many of these interconnections as possible in order to reduce the number of wires between pins. With integrated circuits, it is not the count of gates that determines the cost, but the number and type of integrated circuits used and the number of external interconnections employed in implementation. Designing digital circuits is not a trivial task; many factors come into play. Along with the objectives previously mentioned, manually building the circuit on a circuit board is a tedious, time consuming task.

Greenfield [7] estimates that a circuit with 5 integrated circuits has "... no better than a 50% chance of working, due to wiring errors, when power is first applied." As the complexity of the circuit increases, the probability of the circuit working on the first try decreases rapidly. The process of locating and correcting the faults in a circuit is called "debugging."

Greenfield states that the ability to debug a complex circuit is one criteria which separates the expert engineer from the novice engineer. To debug successfully, one must start by knowing exactly what the circuit is supposed to do and the value for each pin that is wired. By comparing the way the circuit actually works to the way it was designed should reveal the source of errors as either wiring or logic. Wiring errors consist of improperly connected gates, missing connections, and violations of fanout or race conditions. Logic errors, which are more complex to detect, require information about how the chip performs. By functionally decomposing the problem, a solution can be found; conversely, by assembling the partial solutions to a problem, the problem is resolved incrementally.

Expert System Applicability

Expert systems thrive on problems that can be decomposed into

subproblems. In general, an expert system has three main parts: stored knowledge (expertise), an inference engine, and a user interface. The stored knowledge is the fuel for the inference engine. As questions are posed by the user, the inference engine infers partial solutions from the stored knowledge. The sum of the partial solutions provides the completed answer.

An expert system's inference engine is the software that is executed to find the solution. The expertise, or knowledge, about the problem domain is represented in rules. Each rule has a premise and a conclusion. The premise is often referred to as the left-hand side (LHS) of the rule, and the conclusion is called the right-hand side (RHS). The LHS determines the applicability of the rule, and the RHS describes the action to be performed if the rule is applied [20].

The user interface is a critical part of any expert system. The interface should offer easy access to the stored data, rapid execution of problem resolution, and provide a friendly development environment for the user. In the case of digital circuits, information needed to connect chips together could be viewed as knowledge for the expert system. Information such as the number of pins, value of each pin (input, output), type of chip, etc., are readily represented in a database. Evaluating the interconnections between one integrated circuit and another or to itself is beyond the scope of a database, but well within the power of an expert system.

Defining a broad-based debugging tool could prove to be ineffective as the design expands or unique instances occur. Defining a narrow debugging tool could limit the effectiveness of the debugger; therefore, a blend of debugging tools is needed. A two-step approach is proposed that could be used to debug a circuit.

Given a table of all the connections present in a digital circuit, the first step would use database functions to mark all the correct connections leaving the incorrect, questionable, and interconnections among chips for the expert system. The list could then be reduced by removing the correct connections and passing a smaller list into the expert system for the second step of debugging. Errors would be identified by the expert system during the examination of the chip interconnections. This two-step process would combine the speed of database functions with the power of expert systems. The result is a synergistic approach to debugging digital circuits.

Many of the current uses of expert systems in computer-aided design (CAD) work at the component level. Many assume that the circuit is wired properly and limit the aid to component layout or selection. Much of the research in CAD design is in the simulation of designed circuits. Also, considerable research has gone into routing algorithms for the pin connections. Using an expert system to debug a digital circuit at the gate level appears to be a novel idea. None of the digital CAD tools allow the designer to build a circuit in terms of the actual integrated circuits (ICs). We feel that the effectiveness of a CAD tool using an expert system relies in part on the similarity between the CAD tool's representation of the problem and the actual design tasks of the user.

Problem

This research describes the design, construction, and testing of an expert system which detects wiring errors in digital design circuits constructed of 7400 series TTL ICs. The expert system includes a librarian utility which inserts/modifies the working set of IC components.

The issues of interfacing with the graphics package and the user were successfully resolved. The expert system, simulator, and graphics system are operational on the same microcomputer. The expert system provides explicit error detection message files and is able to handle large circuits. Expert system performance is evaluated and the extension of the knowledge domain, to include user-generated design rules, is discussed.

Approach

The first step was examining the current literature regarding CAD development and related expert system developments. This examination was focused on the expert systems embedded in engineering workstations. Four software packages that could host the expert system were examined and evaluated. After the tool was selected, specific data attributes were defined and discussed with the individuals designing the simulator and graphic interface.

Implementation consisted of a combined database and expert system approach. A complete expert system was designed from the ground up and was evaluated with a suite of test cases. These test cases consisted of TTL circuits which were built and tested in a digital logic course taught at the Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT). Additional circuits were built to test for possible limitations on the

size of the circuits. The expert system was modified and extended in an attempt to maximize the effectiveness of the tool as well as the quality of the 'advice'. A librarian feature was incorporated to allow for additions and modifications to the component list. The librarian was implemented in software and can be accessed through the user interface. Additionally, the expert system was integrated with the other theses efforts to create a complete engineering workstation.

Features unique to the expert system in a stand-alone mode include: a natural language interface, the ability to create or edit graphics files, rule base querying on rule firings, trace record of rules fired, and the ability to decouple the control sequence of the expert system.

EXISTING TECHNOLOGY FOR DIGITAL CAD

There are two basic types of electrical circuits, analog and digital. This research examined both cases; however, the primary intended CAD tool is digital circuit analysis.

A research report by McNally [14] reviewed the various methods of working with analog circuits. This report presented a good overall approach to computer-aided design in an analog environment. McNally focused on the uses of SPICE (Simulation Program with Integrated Circuit Emphasis) developed by the University of California at Berkeley. SPICE is a public domain system that deals with floating voltage sources and inductances in an analog circuit. McNally reviewed systems available by eleven companies involved in computer-aided design. Each review provides a snapshot of the capabilities and limits of each design tool.

Several AFIT students examined the effects of an expert system on digital circuits. Estes, Kroll, & Mraz [6] designed and built a prototype in use at AFIT called InterConnect Expert (ICE). ICE is an expert system used to identify wiring errors in a digital circuit by using a rule-based system. Using ICE allows a user to check the wiring of a circuit without having to wire the actual components for verification. ICE is limited to thirty-two integrated circuits (ICs) for circuit design. ICE doesn't have a librarian feature for inserting or deleting ICs.

Electronic Workbench

The 21st Design Automation Conference hosted by IEEE in 1984 yielded some interesting work on current electronic workbench technology by Kelly [11], and Birmingham & Siewiorek [2]. Kelly's work is an exploratory prototype called CRITTER and is used for critiquing digital circuits. It uses an expert system to determine functional correctness, operating speed, timing correctness, and other circuit changes. CRITTER uses three steps to check the circuit. The first step transforms the user's information into the necessary specifications and signals. The second step transforms the data into a central database. Finally, CRITTER composes a cogent critique of whether or not the circuit will work. This type of analysis is necessary to insure circuit correctness before mass-production of a circuit board is initiated.

The work by Birmingham and Siewiorek addressed the issue of designing the entire board layout. MICON (Microprocessor Configurer) provides the designer with a workbench that takes a very high-level design description, and produces a network interconnection list. This list includes all the necessary hardware to design the circuit. The board is then ready for production. In the past, this type of layout was accomplished using manual techniques. The proposed method uses knowledge-based engineering techniques to drastically reduce the time required to produce a circuit board.

Knowledge-Base Systems

An IEEE conference held in 1985 provided a forum for presentations of some of the current issues in circuit design workstations. Two papers germane to knowledge-base techniques in circuit analysis were presented.

Moskowitz [18] of Allied Bendix Aerospace used a knowledge-base approach to design digital electronics. The system he built is called the Logic Designer's Apprentice (LDA). LDA prompts the user for the design parameters of the desired logic element, then identifies a circuit configuration and selects candidate components. LDA uses a unique method for selection or dismissal of candidate components and describes the reasoning behind each decision. The user can override the LDA and install a specific component. Once the circuit is complete, the design is displayed on a graphics terminal. In effect, the system emulates human methods of component selection and interconnection. This system provides an apprentice type mode which assists the user in building the circuit.

Sacher [21] provided a solid foundation for viewing software logic simulation at the microcomputer level. Logic simulation is the process of building a software model of a particular design, exercising the model, then evaluating the results. Sacher's model uses a series of twenty nodes to represent each IC. These nodes are used to represent the present and future states of the IC. The actual simulation of software uses a deductive method of determining the fault detection ability of the test program in diagnosis of the circuit. The simulator is controlled through a menu-driven user interface shell. The system is implemented on an IBM personal computer (PC).

Current Technology

Current technology that is commercially available is limited. Two of the more advanced systems are described below. HIWIRE [10] is a schematic drawing system that adapts to an IBM PC configured with 320K RAM, two disk drives, parallel port printer, and DOS version 2.0 or later. It allows the design engineer to sketch or modify a design during all phases of conceptual development. It utilizes over 700 TTL components and costs \$895.

Hewlett Packard (HP) created the HP Electronic Design System [9]. This system provides more than 3000 components and runs on HP workstations. This system has a capability for networking among a team of project engineers. Networking facilitates the use of shared computer resources. Each workstation can remotely access the central memory, transfer files, and share printers and plotters. The advanced user interface aids of pop-up menus, ICONS, and multiple windows help the user in design of the digital circuits.

Engineering workstations focus on simulation [2,11] as the cornerstone of development. Some systems implement the simulation tools through the use of knowledge-base systems [18,21]. Current technology systems [9,10] focus on the simulation aspects, but rely heavily on solid graphics and friendly user interfaces. These advances in software development address the issues of simulation and graphics; however, current systems neglect to employ expert systems in engineering workstations for digital circuit design.

EXPERT SYSTEM DESIGN

The expert system was designed using the four stage expert system development methodology proposed by Citrenbaum, Geissman, and Schultz [4]. Their design methodology is similar to the Harmon and King development scheme [8] and Metzger's rapid prototyping approach [15]. All of these approaches begin with a problem determination stage, develop a prototype, extend the prototype, and conclude with an integration and maintenance phase. Essentially, each system develops a prototype in the second stage and then extends the prototype in the third stage.

The Citrenbaum method uses four stages: problem determination and specification, initial prototype, expanded prototype, and delivery system. Each stage stresses different features of the expert system. The problem determination and specification stage corresponds to the requirements analysis stage in a conventional software development project. The major objective is to insure that the project will satisfy a real need and be technically feasible. The main steps are to determine whether an expert system approach is suitable for the problem, identify a subset of the problem for the prototype, and identify the knowledge requirements so that the program structures and tools can be evaluated.

The main objective of the initial prototype is to rapidly demonstrate the technical feasibility of the expert system. The initial prototype represents a small version of the completed system. It is designed to test assumptions about how to encode the facts, relationships, and inference strategies. Additional activities in the initial prototyping phase include:

- identifying the experts for the system,
- learning about the problem,
- specifying performance criteria,
- selecting an expert system building tool,
- developing an initial implementation,
- testing the implementation with test cases, and
- a detailed design for the complete expert system.

Once the initial prototype demonstrates that the expert system is feasible, the expanded prototype can be developed. Development should include: expanding the scope of the system, provide I/O interfaces, monitoring system performance, and adding the bells and whistles. The major development problems in this stage tend to be technical in nature. The expert system tool plays a major role in handling technical problems.

The last stage, delivery system, has two main goals: port the expanded prototype system to the target environment, and meeting the software engineering issues of the project. These issues include performance, integration with other systems, portability, modularity, debugging support, and adherence to design standards. The user interface should meet the customized needs and documentation for system maintenance must accompany the final product.

Prototype

Before the design of an initial prototype could begin, several issues were resolved. It was necessary to identify the experts for the system, system performance criteria, and evaluate and select an expert system building tool. The expert knowledge or expertise for the expert system was obtained from Mano [13] and Greenfield [7]. These textbooks provided the elementary rules for digital circuit design. The Texas Instrument TTL Handbook [23] was used for the chip information needed for the database.

The system performance criteria of the expert system consisted of: the identification of wrong connections in the circuit, the identification of missing connections, and any violations of digital design principles such as race conditions or fanout. The system had to be able to evaluate the maximum size circuit built by the graphics package, a circuit of 8 - 10 ICs was used. Finally, the expert system was required to return an echo copy of the ASCII input file along with error messages for wrong or missing connections.

A key step in prototype development is the tool selection for the expert system. There are a wide range of expert system building tools. Four commercially available software packages that could host the expert system were examined. They were: C, OPS5, OPS83, and Guru. A small project was implemented in each candidate language/tool so that the different attributes of C, OPS5, OPS83, and Guru could be examined. All phases of the prototype were implemented and operational in Guru. Several design problems did occur, the main problems were related to the memory constraints of the Z-248 microcomputer. A full discussion of the software capabilities and the development process is given by Wagner [24].

Graphics Interface

The expert system relies heavily on the interface to the graphics package. This interface is depicted in Figure 1. The graphics package places an ASCII file in the DOS environment, then invokes Guru. Guru automatically executes the expert system by invoking a startup file which acts as a mainline program. The expert system uses the input file to start the processing and generates an output file, containing any circuit errors, upon completion. The output file signals the end of execution and control is return to DOS, which invokes the graphics system.

Figure 1. Graphics Interface

Figure 2 is an example of a simple TTL circuit drawn by the graphics package. Each chip has a unique label, such as T001 or T002. The type of TTL is also given, in this case a 74116 and a 7400. The TTL pin numbers have been added for clarity. Note the two types of connections: TTL to TTL and external source to TTL. The entire circuit is built using these two types of connections. These connections are listed in a file and given to the expert system as input data. This file is converted into a Guru table in the input sequence.

Figure 2. TTL Circuit

The processing phase begins by creating a larger table which holds all the initial input data, temporary variables, error comments, and database information. After assembling the pin connections, the system consults the integrated circuit (IC) database to determine what value should be present on each pin. The database is resident in a separate database which in the prototype contains 32 different ICs.

Once the intermediate table is loaded with the input file and database information, a list of the pin connections is created. This list is sorted by chip and pin number then passed to the expert system. The expert system decomposes the circuit chip by chip. The premise follows: in order to verify that a circuit is correct, the expert system must verify each chip. In order to verify that each chip is correct, the expert system must verify each gate. Once each gate of a chip is verified, the next chip is processed. This recursion continues until all the chips are evaluated. Figure 3 shows the circuit decomposition.

Figure 3. Circuit Decomposition

The expert system uses the databases to determine two things: wrong connections and missing connections. Wrong connections detection is a mixture of database functions and expert system commands. Missing connections executes database functions only. The combination of wrong connections and missing connections comprise the debugging feature of the expert system.

Wrong Connections

Wrong connections are determined by a two stage process. Stage 1 uses database commands to evaluate the contents of the connections database. For instance, according to the database, pin 14 of T002 should be connected to power. The circuit information, input from the graphics, shows pin 14 of T002 connected to power. Therefore, the connection is correct and no further processing is required. The first stage only evaluates external connections to TTLs or TTLs connected to external connections. Interconnections between TTLs are evaluated by the expert system. If an error occurs such as pin 14 of T002 connected to ground, it is flagged and processed in Stage 2 along with all the TTL to TTL connections.

Stage 2 handles all the interconnections between TTLs as well as all the errors caught in Stage 1. A rule set is used to categorize the error and generate the error message. A small set of rules were used to capture the occurrence of a TTL to TTL connection, and messages were sent to the error file. The main objective was to test the combination of using database features in concert with rules to evaluate all the circuit's connections. Once all the connections were evaluated control was passed to the 'missing connections' function.

Missing Connections

Missing uses database operations to evaluate the circuit for missing connections. Since a circuit consists of one or more chips, it is necessary to isolate a chip and then inspect its connections. Furthermore, a chip consists of multiple gates; therefore, it is necessary to inspect each gate. In order to verify existing connections and identify missing ones, it is necessary to obtain a 'master' copy of what connections are legal from the database. The database is queried for an IC, when it is found, a smaller database for that component is created to handle the many 'database' requests concerning chip specifics.

The last piece needed for the extended prototype was the definition of the rule set needed by the expert system. The rule set was used to determine whether a circuit connection is correct or not. Since a circuit consists of two types of connections, two matrices of information were formulated. Recall, there are connections which are from an external source to a TTL, and interconnections from one TTL to another TTL.

The graphics system limited the kind and number of external connections. There are 4 kinds of ports that can be connected to a TTL, they are: input, power, ground, and clock. These are connected to 5 kinds of TTL pins: input, power, ground, clock, and output. (TTL pins such as strobe, enable, etc. are treated as input pins). Each connection is labeled as legal or illegal. Some connections that are marked as illegal could be used in a circuit, and the circuit would function. For instance, a clock signal connected to an input leg of a TTL is marked as illegal. This could be legitimate connection; however, the designer of the simulator identified this as an illegal connection. The second kind of connection, TTL to TTL, was handled in the same manner as the external connections. After the rule set was defined, development of the extended prototype began.

Extended Prototype

The biggest hurdle for the extended prototype was the creation of the rule base. Using the two matrices of defined earlier to specify legal and illegal connections, 33 rules were created. The rules fire in a forward-chaining fashion using a numeric priority system. Once the goal is reached execution stops and Guru continues processing the next request. A goal is reached whenever a connection is determined to be legal or illegal. Each rule has a priority associated with its importance. Guru automatically calculates the priority and executes accordingly.

The priorities range from 80 - 95, and were established in a straightforward fashion. The highest priority is given to the rules which decide the kind of connection being considered. This information determines which matrix of connections will be used to evaluate the present connection. Since the majority of connections of a circuit are TTL interconnections (the input of one TTL tied to the output of another TTL), it would be detrimental to the processing speed to make this the lowest priority; therefore, this is one of the first connections checked. On the other hand, it was not enough to verify that an input is connected to an output; what if this connection was to the same gate on the same chip? This violates a digital design principle by creating a race condition. Therefore, along with errors associated with the connectivity of the TTLs, errors such as race conditions and chip fanout were checked.

Once the ruleset was completed, the extended prototype was ready for testing. The same sequence of test circuits used for the initial prototype were used on the extended prototype. No errors were

encountered, the extended prototype was fully operational in a stand-alone mode.

Delivery System

Delivery System is the last stage of the Citrenbaum expert system development methodology. Integration into the workstation, and verification of the design specific requirements was accomplished using the Z-248 microcomputer targeted for use by the engineering students taking a digital circuit design course. The end result was an integrated engineering workstation that allowed the user to graphically design a circuit, submit it to an expert system for analysis, then pass it to a simulator to observe the results. All three systems work in concert or in a stand-alone mode.

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PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The overall performance can best be described as methodical. The solution is straightforward and uses structured programming techniques to evaluate a circuit. The expert system tool can be partitioned to execute some or all of the operations. The interconnection of the programming modules permits execution of a specific phase such as input or output. By segmenting the code into modules, I was able to make changes much easier, run and test specific attributes of the system, and also partition the system for timing specific modules. The timing yielded some interesting results.

The overall performance of expert system appears to function in a linear fashion, as the number of gates or number of chips is increased, there is a linear increase in time. Runtime is sensitive to both the number of gates and the number of ICs. Figure 4 illustrates the linear feature of the expert system.

Figure 4. Runtime as a Function of Circuit Complexity

Viewing the performance from another perspective, if a circuit is built using 32 chips with 2 gates each, taking approximately 20 minutes to execute, what would the effect be if 16 chips were used with 4 gates? Classical digital design advocates using all the gates available before another chip is added. In this case, the 16 chips with 4 gates each executed in approximately 17 minutes.

The point is, if good design techniques are used (such as using all the gates before another chip is added), the expert system will execute in a shorter period of time. If poor design techniques are used, longer execution times occur. These times reflect circuits with no wiring mistakes. If there were 10% wiring mistakes in the 32 chip des, then add 90 seconds (approximately 7% delay). The delay in the 16 chip design is 44 seconds (approximately 5% delay).

Additional testing examined the specific effects of using database

functions in concert with expert system rules. For instance, given a circuit comprised of 6 TTLs and 75 pin connections, the time required to find all the wrong connections using only the expert system was 122 seconds. Using the same circuit, but first executing a database comparison operation, reduces the total time to 45 seconds (10 seconds for the database operation, 35 seconds for the expert system.) The database operation reduces the list of pin connections by removing all the correct connections; therefore, the expert system has a much smaller list to execute. It is concluded that a two step process, combining the speed of database systems and the power of expert systems, results in a synergistic approach to debugging digital circuits. These results were verified across the entire set of test cases. Figure 5 shows the relative amount of runtime devoted to a typical circuit analysis.

8 ICs @ 2 Gates Each

Figure 5. Relative Magnitude of Runtime Effort

Figure 6 shows the percentage of runtime devoted to actual detection of missing and wrong connections across a wide variety of circuit configurations. The vast majority of the time is involved in using the database to drive the expert system rule base. Clearly, performance improvement efforts should be directed at this bottleneck.

Legend: CS/MC: Correct Circuit/Missing Connections
 IC/MC: 10% Incorrect Circuit/Missing Connections
 CS/MC&WC: Correct Circuit/Missing Connections & Wrong Connections
 IC/MC&WC: 10% Incorrect Circuit/Missing & Wrong Connections

Figure 6. Runtime Workload Characterization

Assessment of Surveys

A survey was completed by the students using the engineering workstation to design digital circuits. Questions were directed at

each component of the workstation, at the workstation as a whole, and some general questions regarding the background of the user.

The majority of the users were familiar with how to use a micro-computer, but none had ever used a CAD tool before. Most users were familiar with digital logic design. The responses to the expert system were favorable. Every survey reflected that the expert system provided a correct and complete analysis of the circuit, finding both wrong and missing connections. Some comments were directed at the speed of the expert system. As discussed earlier, the processing time is linked to the size of the circuit; therefore, as the circuit grows in size, the analysis will increase proportionally in time.

The expert system can be executed at any time during design to help the user verify each piece as it is built. Most of the users waited until the entire circuit was designed before invoking the expert system. Many of the users were not aware that the expert system could be used incrementally as the circuit is designed.

Comments regarding the workstation as a whole were also favorable. Many of the users would prefer to use the workstation to design digital circuits rather than design the circuits, by hand, on a circuit board. All agreed that the workstation was easy to use and was helpful.

CONCLUSION

This research demonstrated how basic engineering techniques can be used to decompose a complex problem into smaller, solvable pieces. The performance issues, raised in the previous chapter, can be resolved by better technology. A linear increase in the processing speed should cause a proportional reduction in the processing time since the expert system operates in a linear fashion. The use of database structures add the needed power for handling large amounts of data. The combination of the rule set and database functions provide a powerful tool for solving complex problems.

Future Research

Future research is warranted in two avenues, performance speed and application. Each avenue is not mutually exclusive. As the performance is increased, more applications may be investigated and in some applications the performance speed may not be relevant.

Performance Issues

The speed of the expert system could be dramatically increased by using different hardware. For instance, a ram disk would eliminate the time the disk uses to process the missing connections. Aside from a hardware change, an interface could be designed in Guru which would allow the user to identify specific chips for evaluation (instead of the entire circuit). This would eliminate redundant checking of the same chips. Also, an interface could be designed to evaluate a circuit for only wrong connections. Since missing connections takes approximately 75% of the total time to evaluate a circuit, just checking for wrong connections would save 75% of the total processing time. By directing the scope of the expert system other applications can be examined.

Applications

The current expert system evaluates digital circuits by decomposing them into chips than the chips into gates. This could be raised one level to an entire device; where, the device is comprised of multiple circuits which would be decomposed into chips. This same algorithm could apply for decomposing VLSI circuits. The key point is, by letting the user direct the workload, this algorithm can be applied across a wide range of applications.

In a broader sense, the results of this research effort stimulate interest in the use of expert system technology as a design assistant in concert with traditional computer aided design. The fact that computer technology can relieve the designer of many details of design work is well established. What is not well established is the notion that the same expertise needed to construct automated design tools is the same type of knowledge which can be exploited by a knowledge based system. We feel that the use of expert systems either in concert with a CAD tool dramatically improves the quality and correctness of a design effort.

For example, consider architectural CAD for floor layouts. Once a CAD tool is used to construct the floor space diagrams, the data used to represent the objects is declared in some data structure. It would not be difficult to construct a rule-based system which could detect inadequate window space, poor use of door openings or insufficient wall outlets. Similarly, most any CAD application can be view as a knowledge-based product.

This research has demonstrated the concept of expert system

enhanced CAD and shown an application with considerable advantages. The concept is extendable to other systems and can be tailored to user specific requirements.

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